

Numerical Investigation of Lunar Regolith as Thermal Buffer for a Heat Pipe Reactor

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a numerical investigation of lunar regolith as a thermal buffer for a heat pipe reactor for surface power generation on the Moon. The study, carried out within the Italian Space Agency's *SELENE* project, aims to assess the capability of *in situ* sintered regolith to mitigate temperature fluctuations in the reactor core under variable power demands. A dynamic system model was developed using an object-oriented approach, coupling a point-kinetics module with a finite-volume fuel and heat pipe models connected to a lumped regolith storage component. Transient simulations were performed to analyze power ramp responses with varying regolith mass. Results show that including sintered regolith effectively attenuates fuel temperature oscillations, reducing excursions by tens of degrees. These findings demonstrate the potential of regolith as an efficient thermal inertia medium and provide new insights into the integration of lunar resources with nuclear surface power systems.

Keywords: Space Reactor, Heat Pipes, Lunar Regolith, Thermal Buffer, Object-Oriented Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the renewed international interest in lunar exploration has driven several initiatives aimed at establishing a long-term human presence on the Moon. NASA's Artemis program targets a surface landing at the South Pole by 2027 [1], while the China–Russia International Lunar Research Station [2, 3] envisions a permanent infrastructure by 2035. Within this context, the Italian Space Agency (ASI) has been co-financing *SELENE* (Sistema Energetico Lunare con L'Energia NuclearE) since 2024 [4]. The project is led by ENEA with partners Politecnico di Milano and Thales Alenia Space Italia, and focuses on the concept of the Moon Energy Hub (MEH), which is responsible for the production, storage and transmission of electrical and/or thermal energy with one or more surface nuclear reactors. *SELENE*'s primary objective is to advance the design maturity and technology readiness of all MEH systems, including the reactor, energy conversion, storage, and transmission, in preparation for their future industrialization.

Despite these recent developments, the lunar environment poses major technological challenges for the success of these initiatives. The lack of atmosphere, long day–night cycles, and extreme temperature fluctuations limit the use of traditional solar-based or battery-based solutions [5], which would require several tons of mass to cover a single lunar night [6]. Consequently, alternative generation and storage approaches exploiting *in situ* resource utilization (ISRU) are being investigated. In particular, lunar regolith, the layer of unconsolidated, fragmented rocky debris and dust that covers the entire surface of the Moon, has gained attention as a promising candidate material for multiple applications [7], and its physical properties and potential role as a thermal storage medium are the focus of recent research [8–10].

This work aims at assessing the benefits of using sintered regolith as a thermal buffer for a Heat Pipe Reactor (HPR) with the goal of reducing fuel temperature oscillations caused by the load following requirements of the MEH. Numerical simulations performed in Dymola are used to evaluate the buffer's

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effectiveness in mitigating core temperature fluctuations under variable power demands. This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the modeling methodology adopted for each energy subsystem, Section 3 discusses the results obtained through the dynamic simulations, and Section 4 summarizes the main conclusions.

2. METHODOLOGY

The analysis relies on numerical simulations carried out in *Dymola*, which is based on the *Modelica* modeling language and its object-oriented principles. This environment was selected as the shared simulation framework as it enables the flexible modeling of multi-domain systems and power transients, thus providing valuable insights into the behavior of a lunar surface energy hub under different conditions. The architecture of the study includes: a HPR, a surrounding regolith domain acting as a thermal sink and buffer, and a variable convective power demand defined as boundary condition.

2.1. Heat pipe reactor's core module

This study takes as reference the Heat Pipe Reactor designed by Boccelli et al. [11]. This HPR, shown in Figure 1, is characterised by a monolithic uranium-molybdenum (U-10Mo) fuel, enriched at 19.75% and cooled by sixty sodium-filled heat pipes arranged on a circular lattice. The fuel is surrounded by a beryllium-oxide reflector, that incorporates six control drums. The reactor was designed to operate with an average fuel temperature of 1050 K and a nominal power of 200 kWt. Mitigating temperature oscillations around this operating point is crucial to preserve the safety margin with respect to the fuel melting point (1416 K) and to minimize thermomechanical stresses, such as swelling and thermal creep, which could compromise the fuel integrity under extended operations.

Figure 1. Longitudinal and transversal views of the HPR's core [11].

2.1.1. Core model

The reactor core is modeled in *Dymola* with the objective of capturing the main thermo–neutronic feedback mechanisms while maintaining a level of abstraction suitable for system-level studies. To this end, the original 3D geometry is reformulated into a simplified axisymmetric configuration. Therefore, the core is modeled as a series of concentric rings, alternately composed of fuel and heat pipes. The dimensions of the core were selected such that each heat pipe ring preserves the total cross-sectional area of the original pipes distributed along a reference circumference, leading to fuel mass preservation with respect to the reference 3D configuration. The geometrical parameters obtained from this approach are reported in Table I.

The fuel is discretized using a finite-volume approach, in which thermal conductivity is considered temperature-dependent [12], while density and specific heat capacity are assumed constant. From

Table I. Geometrical parameters of the fuel element.

Zone	Inner radius (cm)	Outer radius (cm)	Heat pipe thickness (cm)	Axial length (cm)	Number of HP
1	0.00	4.38	1.23	35.20	10
2	5.61	10.38	1.23	35.20	22
3	11.62	16.77	0.83	35.20	28

the fuel component, an average temperature is computed and used as input to a point-kinetics model adapted from the TANDEM library [13]. Reactivity feedback is modeled assuming a constant fuel temperature coefficient of -1.01 pcm/K, corresponding to the value evaluated at the nominal operating temperature of 1050 K [11]. This updated reactivity is then used to compute the new reactor power via the point-kinetics equations, and the resulting power is redistributed within the fuel according to an axial profile obtained from Monte Carlo simulations using OpenMC [11]. The normalized axial power distribution is tabulated as a function of the relative fuel axial position and applied to scale the total power. From this, the volumetric power density is obtained, leading to an updated temperature distribution in the fuel. This iterative loop between fuel thermal behavior and neutronic response allows the model to capture the essential feedback mechanisms governing the reactor dynamics.

2.1.2. Heat pipe model

Heat removal from the core is modeled using a heat pipe component derived from the Liquid Conduction Vapor Flow (LCVF) Sockeye model developed at Idaho National Laboratory (INL) [14]. Sockeye couples 1D compressible vapor flow with 2D axisymmetric heat conduction in the wick/liquid and cladding, linked through interfacial heat and mass transfer. In this work, the model is simplified by assuming fully saturated vapor, an appropriate condition for heat pipes in normal operation, which removes the need for the vapor energy equation. Apart from this assumption, the governing equations and closure relations follow the original LCVF formulation.

The Dymola implementation uses a finite-volume local Lax–Friedrichs scheme for vapor flow and a centered finite-volume discretization for 2D conduction. As shown in Figure 2, comparison with the Ivanovskii experiment indicates that the simplified model introduces only a modest accuracy penalty while reducing the computational burden on the solver [15], which is desirable in this type of studies. Each heat pipe ring in the axisymmetric core is represented by a single equivalent heat pipe that receives a power fraction proportional to the number of pipes in the corresponding 3D configuration, preserving the correct energy balance while reducing computational cost. Furthermore, each finite-volume cell of the evaporator features a thermal port connected directly to the corresponding fuel cell, ensuring consistent cell-to-cell heat coupling. Under the transient conditions considered here, the heat pipe component remains robust and sufficiently accurate. Future work will focus on extended transient validation, and explicit modelling of start-up and shut-down regimes, moving toward a fully open-source, object-oriented simulation tool.

2.2. Lunar regolith model

Lunar regolith is the loose, granular material covering the Moon's surface, formed over billions of years by cratering [16]. It consists of fine dust, crushed rock, and other particulate elements, and has been widely studied for potential *in situ* applications such as water extraction [7], habitat construction, and thermal energy storage [17]. Its intrinsic properties make it a possible candidate for high-temperature thermal storage; however, its low mechanical strength and poor thermal conductivity, largely related to its high porosity, pose significant challenges [8]. To address these limitations, recent studies have investigated sintering techniques, using water or sodium chloride as a binder, which can be used in

Figure 2. Comparison of the vapor temperature in the Dymola tool compared to Ivanovskii experiment and LCVF Original model. Digital data obtained from [14].

extraterrestrial environments [9]. Once sintered, regolith can be shaped into solid spheres or blocks, reducing porosity and substantially improving its heat transfer and storage capabilities.

Table II. Lunar regolith properties [8, 9, 17, 18].

Type	Porosity	Density ($\frac{kg}{m^3}$)	Thermal conductivity ($\frac{W}{mK}$)	Specific heat capacity ($\frac{J}{kgK}$)
Loose	0.33	1500 - 1700	0.012	500 - 1500
Sintered	0.1	2000 - 3000	1 - 2.1	800 - 1300

The thermal buffer in the present study is assumed to be made of sintered regolith. It is modeled as a lumped element, represented as a uniform volume at homogeneous temperature, and implemented directly through the Modelica standard library, with a specific heat capacity set to a constant value of $1300 \frac{J}{kgK}$. Future works will focus on a more detailed analysis of this component, encompassing real designs and accounting for spatial effects related to thermal conductivity.

3. RESULTS

The integrated layout of the simulated system is shown in Figure 3. It includes the point-kinetics neutronic module (TANDEM library), the finite-volume fuel and heat pipe models, the regolith thermal capacitor, and the power extraction block. Heat extraction is modeled using a convective component available in the Modelica Standard Library, in which $Q_{flow} = G_c \cdot \Delta T$. The parameter G_c represents the equivalent convective thermal conductance between the heat pipe condenser and the secondary heat removal system (e.g., a Stirling engine or a gas-cooled heat exchanger). From a physical point of view, G_c serves as the control variable for the power demand: an increase in its value corresponds to a higher heat extraction rate, representing a load-following transient where the power conversion system

requires more thermal energy from the reactor to meet an increased power demand of the MENH. As the initial steady-state condition for all transients, the reactor operates at 200 kWt of thermal power with an average fuel temperature of 1050 K.

Figure 3. Final layout of the integrated energy system in Dymola.

The first analysis investigated the transient fuel temperature response to the gradual increase of G_c in the convective heat extraction component, with the regolith buffer mass varying from 100 kg to 1000 kg. The convective conductance G_c is varied through a 10 s ramp signal with an offset of 100 W/K and a height of 25%, representing a variation in the extracted power from the initial steady-state of 200 kWt toward approximately 250 kWt. Figure 4 shows the corresponding fuel temperature evolution. Focusing on the maximum fuel temperature, in the reference case without regolith, the power ramp induces a sharp peak at about 1139 K followed by damped oscillations. As the regolith mass increases, the transient becomes smoother and slower, with full overdamping effect observed above 1000 kg, mass beyond which the benefit of the thermal buffer's inertia saturates. As shown in Figure 5, without regolith, the rapid increase in convective conductance (2.5%/s) induces a sharp overshoot in fission power followed by underdamped oscillations. These fluctuations arise from the interaction between the neutronic feedback delay and the system's thermal inertia: the rapid power excursion initially exceeds the heat removal rate, triggering a feedback correction loop. Instead, the introduction of the sintered regolith buffer mitigates these oscillations, reducing the peak temperature and leading to an overdamped response. In this context, regolith acts as a passive thermal capacitor: during the power ramp, a fraction of the generated heat is absorbed to raise the temperature of the regolith mass, rather than directly increasing the fuel temperature. While the fission power transient is smoothed by this charging process, it eventually converges to the extracted power profile. This overlap at the new steady-state is a visual confirmation that the energy balance is restored and the requested load demand is fully satisfied.

To test the system across a broader operational range, a second analysis was performed with a 1000 kg buffer, varying G_c via a 10 s ramp between -50% and +50% with respect to the nominal offset value of 100 W/K. Figure 6 compares the transient peak temperatures against the new steady-state values. Specifically, the regolith reduces the fuel temperature slope by 30% at high power and up to 95% at lower loads compared to the no-regolith case, resulting in a quasi-linear relationship between extracted power and peak temperature. This linearity could simplify the control logic required for lunar operations, while the suppression of temperature overshoots at high power loads (300 kWt) is critical to prevent the fuel

Figure 4. Fuel temperature evolution for different storage mass under the ramped increase in the extracted power.

Figure 5. Transient evolution of the fission and extracted power under the ramped increase in the extracted power.

from approaching its thermomechanical limits. Ultimately, the regolith exhibits smaller temperature excursions, indicating that part of the transient heat is temporarily stored in the buffer before reaching a new equilibrium, effectively decoupling the immediate fuel response from the rapid load variations. In both simulations, the regolith's high thermal inertia consistently dampens fuel temperature fluctua-

tions across all scenarios. This effect mitigates thermomechanical stresses and preserves critical safety margins against fuel melting, ensuring robust operational flexibility for future lunar energy systems.

Figure 6. Peak fuel (left) and regolith (right) temperatures during transient compared to the respective new steady-state value as a function of the extracted power.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work has investigated the potential use of lunar regolith as a thermal buffer for a HPR operating on the Moon. The integration of a thermal buffer aims to improve stability of the reactor by mitigating fuel temperature excursions during power transients. Simulation results demonstrate that the high thermal inertia of sintered regolith can effectively smooth out the core thermal response, reducing temperature gradients and associated stresses. In addition to its functional benefits, the use of *in situ* regolith offers also a strategic advantage by leveraging on available surface materials, significantly reducing the payload mass that must be delivered from Earth. Future developments will focus on refining the representation of heat pipes, selecting an appropriate geometry for the storage system, and designing the thermohydraulic and mechanical interfaces required to effectively couple the thermal buffer with the HPR and an energy conversion system. In parallel, attention will be devoted to the technical challenges of sintering lunar regolith *in situ*, which remains a critical step for enabling its practical use as a thermal storage medium.

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